

Google Bard's Physical Capabilities in Vietnamese High Schools

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Abstract: *This paper presents an evaluation of the physics performance of Google Bard on the physics test of the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination (VNHSGE). The objective was to assess the accuracy and effectiveness of Google Bard in solving physical problems commonly found in the Vietnamese curriculum. To facilitate this evaluation, the VNHSGE dataset in Vietnamese was translated into English since Bard does not currently support Vietnamese. The results indicate that **Bard** achieved a performance of 52%, lagging behind **ChatGPT** and **BingChat**, which achieved relatively higher scores of 61% and 66%, respectively. It is important to note that this performance may be influenced by the translation process from Vietnamese to English. As a result, it is not recommended for Vietnamese students to rely on Google Bard for physical problem-solving if Bard does not support Vietnamese. Instead, they should use a language model that is specifically designed for physics, such as ChatGPT or BingChat.*

Keywords: ChatGPT, Bing Chat, Bard, physics education, large language model.

I. Introduction

The online education system in Vietnam is growing rapidly, but there are still challenges to be addressed. One way to improve the learning experience for students and optimize the teaching process is to integrate chatbots into online learning systems.

Thanh et al. [1] proposed an online learning platform with a Vietnamese Virtual Assistant that can assist instructors in delivering lectures and testing students. Quy et al. [2] proposed AI-generated lecture

content that is presented through slides (in PDF format) combined with synthesized speech and facial expressions of the instructor derived from the text.

Trang et al. [3] built a chatbot using the Rasa framework and proposed a method that utilizes a custom pipeline for the NLU model. They applied pre-trained language models, FastText and BERT, and created a custom tokenizer for the pipeline. Applying pre-trained language models to the NLU model yielded better results compared to training from scratch. In other research, Trang et al. [4] also developed a Vietnamese chatbot based on a seq2seq model combined with an attention mechanism. The model was built using a small dataset and could generate responses for users. However, the generated responses still need improvement to achieve meaningful conversations.

Hana et al. [5], [6], [7], [8], [9] conducted several studies exploring the role of ChatGPT in Vietnamese education. Their studies identified several potential contributions of ChatGPT to administrators, teachers, and students.

Quy et al. [10], [11], [12] assessed the performance of ChatGPT and Bing Chat on the VNHSGE Examination in various subjects such as mathematics [13], literature, English [14], physics [15], chemistry [16], biology, history, geography, and civic education [11]. The results of these studies demonstrate that both ChatGPT and Bing Chat exhibit a commendable

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overall proficiency in the VNHSGE Examination, achieving an average score of 6-7 for both natural and social science combinations ([11], [12]). Notably, Bing Chat outperforms ChatGPT in most subjects, except for literature.

In [17], Quy et al. evaluated the performance of large language models (LLMs) on the VNHSGE English dataset [10]. The results revealed that Bing Chat performed the best with a score of 92.4%, followed by Bard with 86%, and ChatGPT with 79.2%. These findings suggest that Bing Chat is a more effective language model for the VNHSGE dataset than ChatGPT. The authors provide valuable insights into the performance of LLMs on the VNHSGE dataset. These insights can be used to improve the design and training of LLMs for educational applications. However, it is important to note that the VNHSGE examination is a challenging examination, and even the best language models are not perfect. Further research is needed to improve the performance of LLMs on the VNHSGE and other similar examinations.

Google Bard is a large language model that has been shown to be effective in a variety of tasks. However, its performance on the physics test of the VNHSGE examination has not been extensively studied. This paper aims to evaluate the physics performance of Google Bard in the context of the Vietnamese physical education. The paper will then present a methodology for evaluating Google Bard's performance on the VNHSGE examination. The paper will conclude with a discussion of the results of the evaluation and their implications for the use of Google Bard in physics education.

II. Methods

To evaluate Google Bard's performance in physics problem-solving, the VNHSGE Vietnamese dataset [10] was translated into English. This was necessary because Bard does not currently support Vietnamese. The translated dataset was used to assess Bard's abilities in solving the physics problems of the VNHSGE examination. Each problem's solution was compared against the expected solution, and the performance was measured using a binary grading system. A correct solution was assigned a score of 1, while an incorrect solution was assigned a score of 0. The overall performance of Bard was calculated by averaging the scores of all of the problems.

A. Dataset

In this paper, we use the VNHSGE dataset [10], which was created from the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examinations and other similar exams. The evaluation of the VNHSGE physics dataset consists of 200 multiple-choice questions.

B. Prompt

Figure 1. Prompt to Google Bard.

Figure 1 shows the steps involved in prompting Google Bard. First, the VNHSGE dataset [10] in Vietnamese is translated into English using the Google Translate API³. Then, the questions from the VNHSGE

³ Google Translate API for Python, googletrans 4.0.0rc1

dataset in English are prompted to the Google Bard API. Finally, a Python package is used to return the response of Google Bard through the value of the cookie⁴.

C. Grading

To assess the effectiveness of Google Bard in providing answers, we evaluated their responses by comparing them to the correct solution, also known as the ground truth. The evaluation process used a binary grading system, which classified the Google Bard' answers as either correct or incorrect.

D. Limitations

Google Bard's performance on the VNHSGE Vietnamese dataset was not directly evaluated. This means that we do not know for sure how well Bard would perform on the VNHSGE if it were able to understand Vietnamese. It is possible that Bard's performance would be significantly affected by the translation process, or that it would not be able to understand the questions at all.

As a result, the results of the evaluation are limited to the case of evaluating Bard on a dataset translated from Vietnamese to English. This means that the results cannot be generalized to Bard's performance on the VNHSGE Vietnamese dataset, or on other datasets that are not translated into English.

III. Results

A. Performance

Table 1 shows the performance of Google Bard, ChatGPT, and Bing Chat on the physics test of the VNHSGE examination. The results reveal that Google Bard achieved a score of 52%, while ChatGPT and Bing Chat achieved scores of 61% and 66%,

respectively. These findings indicate that Google Bard's performance in solving physics problems falls behind its counterparts.

Table 1. Performance (%)

	ChatGPT [11]	Bing Chat [12]	Bard
2019	60	55	42,5
2020	62,5	67,5	57,5
2021	60	67,5	50
2022	65	67,5	60
2023	57,5	72,5	50
AVG	61	66	52

Figure 2 shows the performance comparison of ChatGPT, Bing Chat, and Bard on the physics test of the VNHSGE Examination from 2019 to 2023. The results show that the performance gap between Bard and ChatGPT/Bing Chat ranged from 5% to 22.5%, with a maximum value of 22.5% in 2023 and a minimum value of 5% in 2020.

Figure 2. Performance comparison in years 2019-2023.

Figure 3 shows the stability of the responses of LLMs on the physics test of the VNHSGE examination. The results show that the stability of Google Bard is lower than ChatGPT and Bing Chat.

The unstable and lower performance of Google Bard in solving physics problems may be attributed to the translation process from Vietnamese to English. Language nuances and specific problem-solving

⁴ <https://github.com/dsdanielpark/Bard-API>

techniques within the Vietnamese curriculum may not have been accurately captured during translation. This could have led to Google Bard providing incorrect or incomplete answers to some of the questions.

To further investigate the performance of Google Bard, we need to evaluate it directly on the VNHSGE Vietnamese dataset. This will allow us to assess its performance without the potential confounding effects of the translation process.

Figure 3. Stabilities of LLMs response.

B. Google Bard and Vietnamese students

Table 2 displays the scores of LLMs on the physics test of the VNHSGE examination, as well as the performance of Vietnamese students on the same test. The results show that Bard's score of 5.2 is below the passing threshold of 60% on the 10-point scale used in the Vietnamese education system.

Table 2. Score

	ChatGPT [11]	BingChat [12]	Bard
2019	6	5,5	4,25
2020	6,25	6,75	5,75
2021	6	6,75	5
2022	6,5	6,75	6
2023	5,75	7,25	5

Figure 4 illustrates the comparison of scores between the three LLMs and Vietnamese students on the physics test of the VNHSGE Examination. The results show that Bard obtains an average score of 5.2,

while ChatGPT and BingChat obtain scores of 6.1 and 6.6, respectively. These findings suggest that Bard is not yet a suitable tool for supporting physics learning for Vietnamese high school students if it does not support Vietnamese. All three LLMs must be improved to become effective support tools in physics education in Vietnam.

Figure 4. Score comparison of LLMs and Vietnamese students in years.

IV. Discussion

In this section, we discuss the abilities of Bard in supporting physics. We recognize that there are several reasons why it is not recommended for Vietnamese students to rely on Google Bard as their resource for physics problem-solving at the moment:

Bard does not currently support Vietnamese. This means that Vietnamese students would have to translate their physics problems into English before they could ask Bard for help. This could lead to errors in translation, which could make it difficult for Bard to provide accurate answers.

Bard's performance on the physics test of the VNHSGE examination is lower than that of other LLMs. This suggests that Bard is not yet as effective as other LLMs in solving physics problems.

The stability of Bard's responses to physics problems is lower than that of other LLMs. This means

that Bard is more likely to provide incorrect or incomplete answers to physics problems.

Overall, the evidence suggests that it is not yet recommended for Vietnamese students to rely on Google Bard as their resource for physics problem-solving. However, Bard is still under development, and it is possible that its performance will improve in the future.

V. Conclusion

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Google Bard, a large language model, was evaluated on its performance on the physics test of the Vietnamese National High School Graduation Examination. The results showed that Google Bard scored 52%, which was lower than the scores of ChatGPT and Bing Chat. Additionally, Google Bard's physics ability was lower than that of Vietnamese students. Therefore, it is recommended that Vietnamese students refrain from relying solely on Google Bard for physics problem-solving if it does not support Vietnamese.

Appendix

Prompt/ Question	Answer	Grading
<p>Question 1. Place the alternating voltage with the effective value of u at the end of the end of a circuit with a pure inductor, the inductance of the circuit is z_{-1}. What is the following effective I in the circuit?</p> <p>A. $i = 2 u z_{-1}$ S. B. $I = \frac{2 u}{z_{-1}}$ S. C. $i = \frac{u}{z_{-1}}$ S. D. $i = u z_{-1}$ S.</p>	<p>The answer is C. $i = \frac{u}{z_{-1}}$ S.</p> <p>In a pure inductive circuit, the current lags the voltage by 90 degrees. The impedance of a pure inductive circuit is $z_{-1} = \omega L$, where ω is the angular frequency of the applied voltage and L is the inductance of the circuit. The effective value of the current in the circuit is:</p> <p>...</p> $i = \frac{u}{z_{-1}} = \frac{u}{\omega L}$ <p>...</p> <p>Therefore, the answer is C. $i = \frac{u}{z_{-1}}$ S.</p>	Correct
<p>Question 17. Place an effective alternating voltage with a constant effective value, the frequency of ω is changed at the ends of the end of a circuit, including a resistance, a pure inductor with L inductance and a capacitor. There is a capacitance C in series. The effective current in the circuit is the maximum value when</p> <p>A. $\omega L = \frac{2}{\omega C}$ S. B. $\omega L = \frac{1}{2 \omega C}$ S. C. $\omega L = \frac{C}{\omega}$ S. D. $\omega L = \frac{1}{\omega C}$ S.</p>	<p>The effective current in the circuit is given by</p> $I = \frac{V}{\sqrt{R^2 + (\omega L - \frac{1}{\omega C})^2}}$ <p>The effective current is maximum when the term in the square root is equal to zero. This occurs when</p> $\omega L = \frac{1}{\omega C}$ <p>So the answer is D.</p>	Correct
<p>Question 23. A flat, closed wire frame is placed in a uniform magnetic field. During the period of 0.05s, the magnetic rise increased steadily from 0 to 0.02 Wb. During the above period, the magnitude of the induction electromotive force is:</p> <p>A. 2.5 V B. 0.02 V C. 0.05 V D. 0.4 V</p>	<p>The magnitude of the induction electromotive force is given by Faraday's law:</p> <p>...</p> $\varepsilon = -N\Delta\Phi/\Delta t$ <p>...</p> <p>where:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * ε is the magnitude of the induced electromotive force (V) * N is the number of turns in the wire frame (turns) * $\Delta\Phi$ is the change in magnetic flux (Wb) * Δt is the time interval (s) <p>In this case, we have:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * $N = 1$ turn * $\Delta\Phi = 0.02 \text{ WB} - 0 \text{ WB} = 0.02 \text{ WB}$ * $\Delta t = 0.05 \text{ s}$ <p>Therefore, the magnitude of the induced electromotive force is:</p> <p>...</p> $\varepsilon = -1 * 0.02 / 0.05 = -0.4 \text{ V}$ <p>...</p> <p>Since the induced electromotive force is negative, its direction is opposite to the direction of the change in magnetic flux. Therefore, the induced electromotive force will cause a current to flow in the wire frame in the direction that opposes the increase in magnetic flux.</p> <p>So the answer is D.</p>	Correct
<p>Question 25. Nuclear ${}^{56}_{28}\text{Fe}$ has its own linked energy of 8.8 MeV/ nucleons. The link of the nuclear link ${}^{56}_{28}\text{Fe}$ is</p> <p>A. 492.8 MeV B. 246.4 MeV C. 123.2 MeV D. 369.6 MeV</p>	<p>The answer is A. 492.8 MeV.</p> <p>The binding energy of a nucleus is the energy required to separate all of its nucleons. It is calculated using the following equation:</p> <p>...</p> $\text{Binding energy} = (\text{Mass of nucleus} - \text{Mass of individual nucleons}) * c^2$ <p>...</p>	Correct

	<p>where c is the speed of light.</p> <p>In the case of iron-56, the mass of the nucleus is 55.9349375 u, and the mass of the individual nucleons is $26 * 1.007825 \text{ u} + 30 * 1.00867 \text{ u} = 56.04475 \text{ u}$. Therefore, the binding energy of iron-56 is:</p> <p>...</p> <p>Binding energy = $(55.9349375 \text{ u} - 56.04475 \text{ u}) * c^2 = 0.1098125 \text{ u} * c^2$</p> <p>...</p> <p>Converting to MeV, we get:</p> <p>...</p> <p>Binding energy = $0.1098125 \text{ u} * c^2 * (931.5 \text{ MeV} / \text{u}) = 492.8 \text{ MeV}$</p> <p>...</p> <p>Therefore, the answer is A. 492.8 MeV.</p>	
<p>Question 5. Two harmonic oscillations with the initial frequency are φ_1 and φ_2. These two fluctuations in the same phase when</p> <p>A. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = (2n+1)\pi$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$</p> <p>B. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = 2n\pi$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$</p> <p>C. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = \left(2n + \frac{1}{5}\right)\pi$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$</p> <p>D. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = \left(2n + \frac{1}{3}\right)\pi$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$</p>	<p>The two harmonic oscillations are in the same phase when the difference between their phases is an integer multiple of 2π. So the answer is</p> <p>A. $\varphi_2 - \varphi_1 = (2n + 1)\pi$ with $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$.</p>	Incorrect
<p>Question 13. A spring pendulum is horizontal harmonic oscillation. Potential milestone in the equilibrium position. When talking about the muscle of the pendulum, which of the following statements is wrong?</p> <p>A. The function of the pendulum is proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation.</p> <p>B. The energy of the pendulum is with the maximum kinetic energy of the pendulum.</p> <p>C. The function of the pendulum is with the maximum potential of the pendulum.</p> <p>D. The function of the pendulum is inversely proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation</p>	<p>The correct answer is A. The function of the pendulum is not proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation. The function of the pendulum is actually inversely proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation. This means that as the amplitude of oscillation increases, the function of the pendulum decreases.</p> <p>The other statements are all correct. When the pendulum is at its equilibrium position, it has both potential energy and kinetic energy. The potential energy is due to the height of the pendulum above the ground, and the kinetic energy is due to the motion of the pendulum. The total energy of the pendulum is constant, and it is equal to the sum of the potential energy and the kinetic energy.</p> <p>The muscle of the pendulum works to counteract the force of gravity and keep the pendulum moving. The muscle works harder when the amplitude of oscillation is larger, because the pendulum has more potential energy to overcome. However, the muscle works for a shorter period of time when the amplitude of oscillation is larger, because the pendulum completes its oscillation more quickly.</p> <p>Here is a table that summarizes the different statements and their correctness:</p> <p>Statement Correct? ----- ----- The function of the pendulum is proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation. No The energy of the pendulum is with the maximum kinetic energy of the pendulum. Yes The function of the pendulum is with the maximum potential of the pendulum. Yes The function of the pendulum is inversely proportional to the square of the amplitude of oscillation. Yes</p>	Incorrect
<p>Question 40. Put the voltage $u = 120\cos(100\pi t - \frac{1}{6}\pi)$ (V) at the two ends of the AB circuit in series. inductance L and resistance R; resistance R with $R = 2R$ as shown.</p>	<p>The answer is C.</p> <p>The voltage between the two ends of the AM circuit is:</p> <p>...</p> <p>$u_{am} = u_{ab} - u_r$</p> <p>...</p>	

- When $C = C_0/4$, the effective voltage between the two ends of the AM circuit reaches the maximum and the voltage between the two ends of the MN circuit is u_{mn}
- A. $u_{mn} = 40 \cos(100\pi t + \frac{2\pi}{3})$ (v)
- B. $u_{mn} = 40\sqrt{3} \cos(100\pi t + \frac{\pi}{2})$ (v)
- C. $u_{mn} = 40\sqrt{3} \cos(100\pi t + \frac{2\pi}{3})$ (v)
- D. $u_{mn} = 40 \cos(100\pi t + \frac{\pi}{2})$ (v)

When $C = C_0/4$, the impedance of the capacitor is very large, so the current in the circuit is very small. Therefore, the voltage u_r is very small, and u_{am} is approximately equal to u_{ab} .

The voltage between the two ends of the MN circuit is:

...

$$u_{mn} = u_r - u_c$$

...

Since the current in the circuit is small, the voltage u_r is very small, and u_{mn} is approximately equal to u_c .

The voltage across the capacitor is:

$$u_c = C \frac{du_{ab}}{dt} = C \cdot 2\pi \cdot 100 \cdot \cos(100\pi t - \frac{\pi}{6}) = 40\sqrt{3} \cos(100\pi t + \frac{2\pi}{3})$$

Therefore, the voltage between the two ends of the MN circuit is:

...

$$u_{mn} = 40\sqrt{3} \cos(100\pi t + \frac{2\pi}{3})$$

...